

MOLECULAR DETECTION OF CO-PRODUCTION OF ESBL, AMPC AND INTEGRONS AMONG UROPATHOGENS IN A STUDY FROM MUMBAI

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ABSTRACT

Growing incidences of Extended Spectrum β -lactamases (ESBL) producing pathogens are a global issue. They are enzymes capable of hydrolyzing broad spectrum β -lactam antibiotics. In the current study, Phenotypic screening of ESBL producers was done from 747 gram negative uropathogens, among which 167 ESBL producers were identified. Screening of ESBL producers was done with the help of Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing, Phenotypic Confirmatory Disc Diffusion Test, Double Disc Synergy Test and E- Test. Determination of minimum inhibitory concentration of 3rd generation cephalosporins, highlighted 37 ESBL producers to be either sensitive, or exhibit intermediate resistance to ceftazidime, ceftriaxone or cefotaxime. This indicates difficulty in routine ESBL detection where MIC is generally carried out as a screening step for ESBL detection. All ESBL producers showed presence of plasmid of approximately 50-60 kb in size. Confirmation of ESBL production was done by PCR amplification which showed presence of bla_{TEM} (742bp) gene in 156 out of 167 ESBL producers, bla_{CTX-M} (413bp) gene in 63/167 and bla_{AmpC} (346bp) gene in 108/167 ESBL producers. Co-production of multiple β -lactamase genes was observed in 144/167 isolates. Class 1 and 2 integrons were detected in 51/167 (30.53%) and 11/167(7.78%) isolates respectively. Hence our study highlighted high prevalence of co-production of β -lactamases among uropathogens and the inefficiency of MIC as a phenotypic detection method in screening of β -lactamases.

KEYWORDS: ESBL, PCDDT, DDST, PCR, uropathogens, Antibiotic Resistance.

INTRODUCTION

Urinary tract infections have been neglected by health care professionals for a very long time. Urologists, all over the world under estimated the clinical importance of UTIs until the occurrence of Multi Drug Resistant (MDR) uropathogens causing complicated infections. The reason being; the more common occurrence of uncomplicated UTIs and the fact that it is easily treated and cause negligible mortality among patients.^[1] However, recently there has been a tremendous increase in complicated cases of UTIs caused by extremely drug resistant uropathogens that has restricted the use of available antibiotics. It is estimated that over 150 million people get infected with UTIs annually worldwide, making it one of the most common infectious disease.^[2]

Among the nosocomial infections, UTIs contribute to 40% of the cases.^[3,4] Around 13,000 (2.3%) deaths were recorded due to UTIs in the U.S in the year 2014. Also 13% of all the Hospital acquired infections (HAIs) were due to UTIs in the U.S.^[5] In India, such statistical and epidemiological data is not available due to the lack of documentations. However, significant increase in cases of complicated UTIs and also increase in mortality rates have been reported.^[6,7,8]

Recently there has been an enormous report on the occurrence of ESBL producing uropathogens across the globe. "ESBLs are functionally defined as β -lactamases (belonging to Bush's functional group 2be and Ambler molecular class A) able to hydrolyze extended-spectrum cephalosporins (ceftazidime or cefotaxime) and monobactams (aztreonam) at a rate that is equal to or higher than 10% of that for benzyl-penicillin and to be inhibited by β -lactamase inhibitors, such as clavulanic acid, whereas they cannot hydrolyze cephamycins (cefoxitin or cefotetan) or carbapenems (imipenem or meropenem) efficiently".^[9]

ESBLs confer resistance to penicillins, oxyimino-cephalosporins as well as to monobactams. They have very little activity against cephamycins, carbapenems and β -lactamase inhibitors. ESBLs have been observed in several members of Enterobacteriaceae (Enterobacter spp, Salmonella spp, Proteus spp, Citrobacter spp, *M. morgani*, *S.marcescens*, *S.dysenteriae*) as well as in *P.aeruginosa* and *A.baumannii*.^[10]

The transformation of a β -lactamase enzyme to extended spectrum β -lactamases usually follows a point mutation in the bla gene resulting in changes in amino acid

sequences near the enzyme's active site and therefore altered substrate specificity. In addition, alterations in enzyme regulation leading to increased enzyme production or alteration in outer membrane protein porin channels can also contribute to increased resistance.^[11] The numerous β -lactamases are encoded either by the chromosomal genes, or by the transferable genes which are located on the plasmids, or transposones.^[12] Beta-lactamases and their mutated forms such as ESBLs and AmpC β -lactamases represent a major cause of multidrug resistance among enteric bacteria. Following selective pressure due to widespread use of β -lactam antibiotics in clinical practice, genes for β -lactamases have evolved at a very rapid pace with over 1300 unique β -lactamases reported in clinical isolates.^[13]

This study will help in understanding the molecular basis of spread of antibiotic resistance in Mumbai by giving an overview of the most prevalent ESBL genes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of samples from Mumbai city

A total of 747 gram negative urine sample isolates were collected from 3 government tertiary care hospitals, 4

private hospitals and 8 pathological laboratories situated in Mumbai during September 2011- January 2014.

Phenotypic screening and confirmation of ESBL producers

All the isolates showing resistance to 3rd generation cephalosporins, viz. ceftazidime, ceftriaxone and cefotaxime, were phenotypically tested for ESBL production by Double Disk Synergy test (DDST) and Phenotypic Confirmatory Disk Diffusion Test (PCDDT) and, confirmation of ESBL production was done using E-test. A part of this study, including phenotypic characterization of 68 ESBL producers has been described in a previous study.^[14]

Determination of Minimum Inhibition Concentration

The MIC of 3 antibiotics viz. ceftazidime, ceftriaxone and cefotaxime were determined against ESBL producers using E-strip (Hi Media Laboratories Pvt. Ltd.) with a concentration gradient of 0.5-256 mcg/ml. Antibiotics susceptibility determination criteria as per CLSI guidelines are indicated in Table 1.^[15]

Table 1: Antibiotic susceptibility criteria of third generation antibiotics indicated by CLSI guidelines.

Antibiotics	Organisms	Susceptible	Intermediate	Resistant
Ceftazidime	Enterobacteriaceae	≤ 4 mcg/ml	8mcg/ml	≥ 16 mcg/ml
	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	≤ 8 mcg/ml	16mcg/ml	≥ 32 mcg/ml
Ceftriaxone	Enterobacteriaceae	≤ 1 mcg/ml	2mcg/ml	≥ 4 mcg/ml
	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	≤ 8 mcg/ml	16-32mcg/ml	≥ 64 mcg/ml
Cefotaxime	Enterobacteriaceae	≤ 8 mcg/ml	16-32mcg/ml	≥ 64 mcg/ml
	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	≤ 8 mcg/ml	16-32mcg/ml	≥ 64 mcg/ml

Extraction of plasmids

Plasmid extraction was carried out from overnight grown ESBL producing uropathogens by SDS method.^[16] The extracted plasmids were treated with RNase (10mcg/ml) and then re-precipitated with 0.1 volume of 3M sodium acetate (pH 5.2) and two volumes of ethanol. The RNase free plasmids were run on 1.2% agarose gel and visualized under UV, using Gel Documentation System to check for presence of plasmid DNA.

Amplification of antibiotic resistant genes by PCR

Amplification reactions were performed in a 25 μ l reaction mixture volume, containing 2.5 μ l of 10X PCR reaction buffer, 1.5 μ l (1.5mM) MgCl₂, 0.5 μ l (200 μ M) deoxy-nucleotide triphosphate-mix (dNTPs), 1 μ l (10pM)

forward as well as reverse primers (mentioned in Table 2) and 1 μ l (3U/ml) of the Taq DNA polymerase (Bangalore Genie TM, India). The plasmid DNA (1 μ l) extracted from the ESBL producers were used as template and the reaction volume was made up to 25 μ l using sterile double distilled water. The reaction mixture was subjected to PCR amplification using a MyCycler DNA thermal cycler (Eppendorf). The resultant PCR products were analyzed by agarose gel- electrophoresis using a 2% agarose gel prepared in TAE (Tris-Acetate-EDTA) buffer, containing 5 μ l ethidium bromide (5mg/ml).^[16] A molecular weight marker (100bp DNA ladder) was also included in the gel to confirm the amplicon size. All results were documented using a Gel Documentation System post- electrophoresis.

Table 2: List of primers used in the study.

Target	Primer name	Primer sequence	Annealing temperature (°C)	Amplicon size
bla _{TEM}	TEM-F	5'-ggt gaa agt aaa aga tgc tg-3'	54	742 bp
	TEM-R	5'-acc aat gct taa tca gtg ag-3'		
bla _{SHV}	SHV-F	5'-atg cgt tat att cgc ctg tgt a-3'	63	725 bp
	SHV-R	5'-tta gcg ttg cca gtg ctc gat c-3'		
bla _{CTX-M}	CTX-M-F	5'-ctt agc gcg gcc gcg cta ca-3'	65	413 bp

	CTX-M-R	5'-acc aga atc agc ggc gca cga-3'		
bla _{Amp-C}	AmpC-F	5'-aac agc ctc agc agc cgg tta-3'	62	346 bp
	AmpC-R	5'-ttc gcc gca atc atc cct agc-3'		
bla _{Int-1}	Int1-F	5'-cag tgg aca taa gcc tgt tc-3'	55	180 bp
	Int1-R	5'-ccc gag gca tag act gta-3'		
bla _{Int-2}	Int2-F	5'-ttg cga gta tcc ata acc tg-3'	55	287 bp
	Int2-R	5'-tta cct gca ctg gat taa gc-3'		

Analysis of the PCR products

The PCR amplicons were sequenced by using corresponding primers for specific genes listed in Table 2 and the entire sequence of each gene was compared with sequences in the GenBank nucleotide database using the blast software available at <http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>. Sequencing of the PCR amplicons was carried out at Sci. Genomics Pvt. Ltd, Cochin, Kerala, India.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Detection of ESBL producers

Our previous study reported the prevalence of *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* among total isolated uropathogens (Table 3) which was found to be 59.57% and 16.19% respectively.^[17]

Table 3: Total uropathogens isolated from Mumbai.

Pathogens	Total no. of isolates	ESBL producer
<i>E. coli</i>	445	106
<i>K. pneumoniae</i>	121	25
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	44	4
<i>P. vulgaris</i>	15	3
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	67	15
<i>C. amalonaticus</i>	7	1
<i>C. diversus</i>	37	12
<i>E. aerogenes</i>	1	1
<i>E. cloacae</i>	1	-
<i>E. fecalis</i>	1	-
<i>M. morgani</i>	4	-
<i>A.baumani</i>	4	-
Total	747	167

Table 4: MIC of 3rd generation antibiotics against ESBL producers.

Test isolates	Ceftazidime			Cefotaxime			Ceftriaxone		
	S	I	R	S	I	R	S	I	R
<i>E.coli</i> (n=106)	2	9	95	9	2	95	3	-	103
<i>K.pneumoniae</i> (n=25)	3	1	21	3	-	22	3	-	22
<i>P.aeruginosa</i> (n=15)	-	-	15	-	-	15	-	-	15
<i>Proteus spp.</i> (n=7)	-	-	7	-	-	7	-	-	7
<i>Citrobacter spp.</i> (n=13)	2	-	11	-	-	13	-	-	13
<i>E.aerogenes</i> (n=1)	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1

S- sensitive; I-intermediate; R-resistant.

In the current study, 91.61% and 96.40% isolates were found to be resistant to cefotaxime and ceftriaxone respectively. Resistance to these antibiotics is mainly associated with the expression of CTX-M and CMY-2 gene respectively.^[18,19] However, in certain cases presence of multiple β -lactamase genes may also be

Determination of MIC

The MIC values of 3rd generation cephalosporins against ESBL producers are indicated in Table 4. Determination of MIC by E-test method showed 161/167 isolates to be resistant to ceftriaxone. Resistance to ceftazidime and cefotaxime was also observed among 150/167 and 153/167 ESBL producers respectively. Also, among the ESBL producers, 12/167 isolates showed intermediate resistance and 25/167 isolates showed sensitivity towards ceftazidime, cefotaxime and/or ceftriaxone.

This indicates that ESBL production may not be associated with complete resistance to cephalosporin antibiotic; moderately resistant as well as sensitive strains may also be potential ESBL producers. In addition, almost all of the isolates resistant to cefotaxime and ceftriaxone showed extremely high MIC of >256mcg/ml. However such high degree of resistance was observed in comparatively few (i.e 45) ceftazidime resistant isolates.

specific gene. Many genes like CTX-M^[21] and Integron IBC-2^[22] have been shown to be associated with resistance to ceftazidime.

Similar results have been reported in another study where, screening test result for ESBL production revealed that four cefpodoxime sensitive, six cefotaxime sensitive, 11 ceftazidime sensitive and 9 aztreonam sensitive isolates were ESBL positive on confirmatory test.^[23] Another study carried out in an ICU in France, also reported low level resistance to cephalosporins among ESBL producing uropathogens. They further confirmed that; although the cephalosporin MICs were in the susceptible range, they were substantially higher than the MICs for non-ESBL-producing strains at their hospital.^[24]

Unlike all ceftriaxone and cefotaxime resistant isolates, only 45/167 (26.9%) ceftazidime resistant isolates showed elevated MIC (i.e >256mcg/ml) in our study. In another study carried out by Vu and Nikaido, (1985), it was observed that the over-production of class C β -lactamases i.e AmpC were associated with elevated resistance to ceftazidime.^[25] Queenan et al. (2010) also showed increased activity of AmpC β -lactamases in ceftazidime resistant mutants.^[26] In our study too, perfect correlation was observed between the production of AmpC β -lactamase and elevated resistance to ceftazidime (Data not shown). In another study, AmpC over-production has been reported in 88% ceftazidime resistant *P.aeruginosa*.^[27]

Moreover, restoration of OmpK36 function in porin-deficient strains of ESBL producing *K.pneumoniae* causes significant decreases in the MICs of ceftazidime, indicating a possible relation between loss of this porin and elevated MICs of ceftazidime in *K.pneumoniae*.^[28] In *E.coli*, loss of either of the OmpC or OmpF porins is responsible for resistance to cephalosporins.^[29]

In our study, 7 ceftazidime sensitive and 10 ceftazidime intermediate isolates were found to be ESBL producers. The ceftazidime sensitive isolates i.e *E.coli* (isolate no. 262, 264), *C.diversus* (isolate no.124, 644) and *K.pneumoniae* (isolate no. 275, 507, 536) showed their MIC in the range of 2-4mcg/ml. Except for *E.coli* isolate 262 and 264, all other ceftazidime sensitive isolates showed MIC to be >256mcg/ml towards ceftriaxone. Also, *K.pneumoniae* isolate 275 showed sensitivity to ceftazidime and cefotaxime but was found to be resistant to ceftriaxone (with MIC >256mcg/ml). Higher susceptibility to ceftazidime among ESBL producers has also been reported by Rao et al. (2014) where 493 (80.3%) and 486 (79.1%) isolates of ESBL producing *E.coli* were found to be resistant to ceftriaxone and cefotaxime respectively. However, only 228 (37.1%) isolates showed resistance to ceftazidime.^[30] Similar observations were noted for ESBL producing *K.pneumoniae* in the same study, where 382 (82.7%) and 343 (74.2%) isolates showed resistance to ceftriaxone

and cefotaxime respectively. However, only 253 (54.8%) isolates showed resistant to ceftazidime.^[30] It has been observed that the CTX-M β -lactamases hydrolyze ceftazidime with a very low catalytic efficiency. Thus, CTX-M β -lactamases may confer high levels of resistance to cefotaxime and ceftriaxone but at the same time exhibit marginal effect on the MIC of ceftazidime.^[18] As observed in the current study all the above ceftazidime sensitive isolates, except *K.pneumoniae* (isolate no. 275), showed presence of CTX-M gene; thus explaining the difference in the MIC of the tested 3rd generation cephalosporins.

Amplification of antibiotic resistant genes

Plasmid DNA obtained from ESBL producing uropathogens was used as a template to amplify bla_{TEM}, bla_{CTX-M}, bla_{SHV}, bla_{AmpC}, bla_{Int1} and bla_{Int2} genes using its specific primers listed in table 2. These were seen as discreet bands on 2% agarose gels when visualized under UV. PCR amplification showed presence of bla_{TEM} (742bp) gene in 156 out of 167 (Fig. 1), bla_{CTX-M} (413bp) gene in 63/167 (Fig. 2) and bla_{AmpC} (346bp) gene in 108/167 (Fig. 3) ESBL producers. Co-production of multiple β -lactamase genes was observed in 144/167 (86.22%) isolates. Class 1 (180bp) and 2 (287bp) integrons were detected in 51/167 (30.53%) and 11/167(6.58%) isolates (Fig. 4 and 5) respectively. Co-production of Class 1 and 2 integrons together was not observed in any of the isolates.

Amplification of ESBL genes

In the current study, bla_{TEM} was the most prevalent gene observed in 92.21% ESBL producing isolates followed by bla_{AmpC} and bla_{CTX-M} which was present among 64.07% and 37.12% isolates respectively. bla_{SHV} was not detected in any of the isolates. Among the most common uropathogens i.e *E.coli* and *K.pneumoniae*, bla_{TEM} was amplified in 91.50% and 84% isolates respectively. Also among the ESBL producing *E.coli*, 40.56% isolates harboured bla_{CTX-M} and 59.43% isolates harboured bla_{AmpC}. Among the ESBL producing *K.pneumoniae*, bla_{CTX-M} and bla_{AmpC} was observed in 28% and 68% isolates respectively.

In a similar study, Lim et al. (2009) has reported that majority of the ESBL positive isolates from Malaysia harbored bla_{TEM-1}(88%) followed by bla_{CTX-M} (20%) and bla_{SHV} (8%).^[31] Bali et al. (2010) reported bla_{TEM} in 72.72% of *E. coli* and 75% of *Klebsiella* spp., while they reported 9.09% and 22.72% production of bla_{SHV} and bla_{CTX-M} respectively among clinical isolates in Turkey.^[32] Yushau et al. (2007), reported prevalence of ESBL producers in 9.3% clinical isolates in Kano, Nigeria.^[33]

In a study carried out in a rural district of Rajasthan; of the 20 ESBL positive *E.coli* isolates, 60% harbored bla_{TEM}, 55% harbored bla_{SHV} and 80% harbored bla_{CTX-M} as detected by PCR, and of the 20 ESBL positive *Klebsiella* spp. isolates 75% harbored bla_{TEM}, 60%

harbored bla_{SHV} and 85% harbored bla_{CTX-M}.^[34] In another study carried out by the same authors in a tertiary care hospital in Chandigarh, bla_{TEM} and bla_{SHV} was observed in 60% and 72% *Klebsiella* spp. and 52% and 48% *E. coli* respectively.^[35]

The high prevalence of bla_{CTX-M} is also reported by Vaida et al. (2010) among majority of ESBL producing *E. coli* (96%) and *K. pneumoniae* (71%).^[36] It has been observed that bla_{CTX-M} is the most prevalent ESBL-encoding gene worldwide and is replacing TEM and SHV types as the predominant ESBL gene in many European and Asian countries.^[37,38]

Fig: 1. Amplification of bla_{TEM} (742bp) by PCR.

Lane 1: 100bp ladder; Lane 2-12: Genes amplified from *E. coli* isolates 20, 23, 32, 35, 39, 51, 63, 83, 84, 87 and 94 respectively

Fig:2. Amplification of bla_{CTX-M} (413bp) by PCR.

Lane 1: 100bp ladder; Lane 2-5: genes amplified from *C. diversus* isolates 15, 28, 30 and 58 respectively; Lane 6-10: genes amplified from *E. coli* isolates 79, 83, 87, 96 and 115 respectively.

Fig: 3 Amplification of bla_{AmpC} (346bp) by PCR.

Lane 1: 100bp ladder; Lane 2-10: Genes amplified from *E. coli* isolates 20, 23, 32, 35, 39, 51, 63, 84, 94 respectively.

Fig 4. Amplification of bla_{Int1} (180bp) by PCR.

Lane 1: 100bp ladder; Lane 2-12: genes amplified from *C. diversus* isolates 15, 28, 30, 58, 102, 116, 120, 124, 497, 500 and 644 respectively.

Fig 5. Amplification of bla_{Int2} (287bp) by PCR.

Lane 1: 100bp ladder; Lane 2-10: genes amplified from *E. coli* isolates 79, 83, 87, 148, 190, 220, 238, 245, 249 respectively; Lane 11: genes amplified from *K. pneumoniae* isolate 730.

Kiratisin et al. (2008) has also reported increasing trends in the prevalence of CTX-M ESBLs. They reported that the prevalence of bla_{CTX-M} was strikingly high in their study with 99.2% of ESBL-producing *K. pneumoniae* carrying the same.^[39]

In contrast to these findings where bla_{CTX-M} was found to be the most prevalent gene, our study showed bla_{TEM} to be the most prevalent gene among *E.coli*, *K.pneumoniae* as well as other ESBL producing Enteriobacteriaceae. The difference in our findings may be explained by the fact that the epidemiology of antibiotic resistant bacteria varies from region to region and from one infection type to another. It also differs from one year to another.^[40] It is for this reason that no two studies show similar prevalence of resistance genes if carried out at different time periods at different locations, and hence constant monitoring of antibiotic resistance is required.

Variations in the prevalence of other ESBL genes have been reported worldwide. Molecular analysis of ESBL genes carried out by Zaniani et al. (2012) at Mashhad University of Medical Sciences, Iran revealed presence of 20.6% bla_{TEM} and 14.4% bla_{SHV} type ESBL producers in their study.^[41] Another study carried out by Anago et al. (2015) reported 77.4% bla_{TEM} and 20.2% bla_{SHV} producing *E.coli* in a tertiary care centre in Cotonou, Benin.^[42] Ahmed et al. (2013) reported 10% isolates to carry bla_{SHV} and 53.3% isolates to carry bla_{CTX-M} in a tertiary care hospital in Egypt.^[43] Jemima and Verghese, 2008 performed multiplex PCR for detection of bla_{CTX-M} and bla_{SHV} from 62 ESBL producing *Klebsiella* spp. Results showed presence of bla_{SHV} in 45% and bla_{CTX-M} in 40% clinical isolates of *Klebsiella* spp.^[44]

Co-production of Multiple ESBL genes

In the present study, it has been observed that 37/167 (22.15%) isolates carried more than one ESBL genes i.e bla_{TEM} + bla_{CTX-M} (Table 5). Presence of multiple resistance genes allow the pathogen to exhibit resistance to more than one or, similar group of antibiotics resulting in more serious infections. This is a matter of great concern, especially because of the fact that dissemination of β -lactamase producing strains are commonly observed

in hospitals as well as community settings due to presence of these resistance determinants on mobile genetic elements like plasmids and transposons. Hence if detection of ESBL producers is not routinely carried out in hospitals (which are the scenario in most of the healthcare centres), the occurrence as well as dissemination of these resistance factors remain undetected and hence, the pathogens are more likely to acquire multiple resistant determinants in the form of plasmids or, by vertical transfer of genetic information.^[45,46]

In a study carried out by Goyal et al. (2009), majority of strains (57.3%) harbored 2 or more ESBL genes,^[47] while Bali et al. (2010) observed that 19.2% ESBL isolates carried more than one type of β -lactamase genes.^[32] In another study by Sharma et al. (2013), it has been observed that 31 out of 40 (77.5%) isolates carried more than one type of β -lactamase genes with 13 (32.5%) isolates harboring all the three β -lactamase genes (bla_{TEM}, bla_{CTX-M} and bla_{SHV}), 9 (22.5%) isolates harboring bla_{TEM} and bla_{CTX-M}, 6 (15%) isolates harboring bla_{SHV} and bla_{CTX-M} and 3 (7.5%) isolates harboring bla_{TEM} and bla_{SHV}.^[48]

A study carried out by Agamy et al. (2009), reported co-production of bla_{TEM} and bla_{SHV} among 56.8% of the isolates, bla_{TEM} and bla_{CTX-M} among 2.27% of isolates, bla_{SHV} and bla_{CTX-M} among 9.1% isolates. All three genes were detected in 25% of 220 isolates in his study carried out in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.^[49] Kaur and Aggarwal, (2013) studied 93 phenotypically confirmed ESBL producers in their study carried out in North India. The molecular characterization revealed that 44.08% isolates possessed the bla_{CTX-M} alone, while the bla_{CTX-M} and the bla_{SHV} together were found in 20.43% isolates. All three genes i.e bla_{TEM}, bla_{CTX-M} and bla_{SHV} were present among 6.45% isolates.^[50]

A recent study carried out in Nepal reported co-production of multiple ESBL genes among 37.5% cases.^[51] Similar study in Taiwan reported co-existence of two or more kinds of ESBL in 40.6% of ESBL producing *E.coli*.^[52]

Table 5: Amplification of ESBL and AmpC genes among uropathogens.

Pathogens	Total	ESBL	β -lactamase genes							
			bla _{TEM}	bla _{CTX-M}	bla _{AmpC}	bla _{Int1}	bla _{Int2}	bla _{TEM} + bla _{CTX-M}	bla _{TEM} / bla _{CTX-M} + bla _{AmpC}	bla _{TEM} + bla _{CTX-M} + bla _{AmpC}
<i>E.coli</i>	445	106	99	27	86	10	10	14	80	9
<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	121	25	24	10	14	10	1	7	16	1
<i>P.mirabilis</i>	44	4	4	-	4	-	-	-	4	-
<i>P.vulgaris</i>	15	3	3	3	-	3	-	2	-	-
<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	67	15	13	9	-	15	-	7	3	-
<i>C.amalonaticus</i>	7	1	1	1	-	1	-	1	-	-
<i>C.diversus</i>	37	11	11	11	4	11	-	6	4	4
<i>E.aerogenes</i>	1	1	1	-	-	1	-	-	-	-
<i>E.cloacae</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>E.fecalis</i>	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

<i>M.morganii</i>	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>A.baumannii</i>	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	747	167	156	63	108	51	11	37	107	14

Prevalence of Amp-C β -lactamases and its co-production with ESBL producers

In the present study, it has been observed that 145/167 (86.82%) isolates carried more than one type of β -lactamase genes which is quite high as compared to previous studies but in accordance with Sharma et al. (2013).^[48] Our study further indicated, 14 (8.38%) isolates to harbour all three β -lactamase genes (bla_{TEM} , bla_{CTX-M} and bla_{AmpC}) (Table 5). AmpC was produced by 108/167(64.67%) isolates. Co-production of AmpC with other β -lactamases was found to be in 107/167 (64.07%) isolates. This is an alarmingly high percentage observed in our study; the reason being the association of AmpC producers with complicated infections and, undetected ESBL phenotypes. In a recent study from Punjab, the AmpC production was seen in 5.4% isolates.^[53] The current study shows comparatively high production of AmpC among uropathogens in Mumbai. A study carried out in Manipal reported a co-production of β -lactamase and AmpC among 58.5% *E. coli*, whereas a study from Bangalore reported a co-production rate of 30.1% for *E. coli* and 30.3% for Klebsiella spp.^[54,55]

To date, AmpC has been found mainly in clinical isolates obtained from hospitalized patients.^[56,57] Tumbarello et al. (2008) has reported more common occurrence of AmpC producing *E.coli* and *K.pneumoniae* from surgical sites. In his study, more than 50% of AmpC producing *E.coli* and *K.pneumoniae* were isolated from surgical sites. In outpatients, the incidence of AmpC producing isolates was found among 18.88% *E. coli* and 8.33% *K. pneumoniae*.^[58]

Amplification of Integron class 1 and 2

Integron-borne β -lactamases particularly pose an increasing threat to the nosocomial environment, giving rise to multi-drug resistant microbes with complex resistance patterns. It has become imperative that we should continuously strive to understand these complex mechanisms of antimicrobial resistance, not only to overcome them, but to avoid them from evolving further.^[86] In our study, class 1 and 2 integrons were detected in 51/167 (30.53%) and 11/167(6.58%) isolates respectively. Co-production of class 1 and 2 integrase genes together was not observed in any of the isolates. Table 6 represents the list of ESBL and AmpC producers along with co-produced class 1 and 2 integrons.

Table 6: List of ESBL and AmpC producers along with co-produced integrons.

Sr. No	Isolate no.	Identified as	ESBL genes present	Integron	FG	CF	RP
INTEGRON 1							
1	15	<i>C.diversus</i>	CTX-M	Int 1	4 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
2	28	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, AmpC, CTX-M	Int 1	128 (R)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
3	30	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	32 (R)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
4	58	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	4 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
5	59	<i>C.amalonatus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	4 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
6	68	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
7	73b	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM	Int 1	16 (R)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
8	93	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	16 (I)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
9	96	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	2 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
10	100	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	2 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	1 (S)
11	102	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, AmpC, CTX-M	Int 1	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
12	115	<i>E.coli</i>	CTX-M	Int 1	2 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
13	116	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, AmpC, CTX-M	Int 1	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
14	120	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, AmpC, CTX-M	Int 1	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
15	123	<i>C.diversus</i>	CTX-M	Int 1	4 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
16	124	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	4 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
17	130	<i>P.vulgaris</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	4 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
18	134	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM	Int 1	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
19	147	<i>E.coli</i>	CTX-M	Int 1	2 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
20	156	<i>P.vulgaris</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
21	160	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
22	166	<i>P.vulgaris</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
23	175	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	16 (I)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
24	196	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	16 (I)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
25	202	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM	Int 1	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
26	204	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)
27	208	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	CTX-M	Int 1	8 (S)	≥ 256 (R)	≥ 256 (R)

28	214	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	16	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
29	216	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	16	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
30	227	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
31	233	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	32 (R)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
32	234	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
33	246	<i>E.coli</i>	CTX-M	Int 1	2 (S)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
34	254	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	4 (S)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
35	265	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	16 (I)	16 (I)	0.5 (S)
36	271	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM	Int 1	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
37	281	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM	Int 1	34 (R)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
38	290	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	CTX-M	Int 1	2 (S)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
39	306	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
40	447	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	8 (I)	≥256 (R)
41	453	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM	Int 1	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
42	497	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
43	500	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	4 (S)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
44	536	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
45	593	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM	Int 1	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
46	644	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	4 (S)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
47	687	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM	Int 1	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
48	741	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	8 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
49	742	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	CTX-M	Int 1	2 (S)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
50	743	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	16 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
51	744	<i>K pneumonia</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 1	32 (R)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
INTEGRON 2							
52	60	<i>E.aerogenes</i>	TEM	Int 2	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
53	79	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 2	8 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
54	83	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 2	4 (S)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
55	87	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 2	8 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
56	148	<i>E.coli</i>	CTX-M	Int 2	2 (S)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
57	190	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM,CTX-M	Int 2	8 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
58	220	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 2	4 (S)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
59	238	<i>E.coli</i>	CTX-M	Int 2	2 (S)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
60	245	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 2	64 (R)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
61	249	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM	Int 2	64 (R)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)
62	730	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M	Int 2	8 (I)	≥256 (R)	≥256 (R)

*FG: Ceftazidime; CF: Cefotaxime; RP: Ceftriaxone; Mer: Meropenem.

S: sensitive; I: Intermediate; R: Resistant.

All isolates with integrase genes showed ≥ 256 mcg/ml MIC for cefotaxime and ceftriaxone except for isolates 100 (*K.pneumoniae*), 265 (*P.aeruginosa*) and 447 (*K.pneumoniae*). However, 42 out of the total 62 isolates with integron class 1 or 2 genes showed MIC of ceftazidime in the sensitive or intermediate range (Table 6). This may be due to the presence of CTX-M genes in all these isolates that confers low degree of resistance against ceftazidime. It has been observed that the CTX-M β -lactamases hydrolyze ceftazidime with a very low catalytic efficiency. Thus, CTX-M β -lactamases may confer high levels of resistance to cefotaxime and ceftriaxone but at the same time exhibit marginal effect on the MIC of ceftazidime.^[18] The low MIC observed towards these antibiotics may also be due to presence of porins or other factors that generally lowers the MIC of antibiotics against the pathogens.

Class 1 integrons are most prevalent in clinical isolates, carrying single or multiple gene cassettes. Integron

inserted genes encode for various antibiotic resistance mechanisms, including over 40 distinct genes, conferring resistance towards aminoglycosides, beta-lactams, chloramphenicol, macrolides, sulphonamides, antiseptics and disinfectants.^[59,28]

Concerning beta-lactamases, integron-borne gene cassettes have been found mainly in *P.aeruginosa*, *A.baumannii* and various Enterobacteriaceae species encompassing Ambler classes A (except TEM and SHV types), B and D beta-lactamase enzymes, giving rise to widespread β -lactam resistance.^[60,18]

Table 7 represents the antibiotic resistance profile of the uropathogens harbouring the Integron class 1 or 2. In our study, 11 ESBL producing uropathogens were found to be resistant to all 24 antibiotics screened. All these isolates showed presence of class 1 or 2 integrons. High degree of resistance was also observed towards other β -lactam as well as non-beta lactam antibiotics. Leverstein

et al. (2002) has also reported the presence of an integron to be significantly associated with multidrug resistance where 10 of the 11 isolates were resistant to ampicillin, 8 were resistant to trimethoprim, 2 were resistant to amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, 2 were resistant to cefuroxime, and 1 was resistant to gentamicin.^[61]

Although integrons are considered to be natural expression vectors, great variability of the expression level of integrated gene cassettes is exhibited. This variability is linked to the intrinsic structures of both gene cassettes and integrons.^[62] Gene expression in an integron is dependent on various factors including promoter strength, gene copy number, the relative distance of the gene cassette from the promoter, and the

presence of additional internal promoters.^[28,59] Expression is usually mediated via a common promoter situated upstream (5' end) of gene cassettes, rather than through individual promoters. Higher levels of gene expression can be achieved if a second promoter is included adjacent to the first, or if the gene in question is included as multiple copies.^[63] The relative distance between a gene cassette and the promoter plays a significant role regarding expression, proximal genes tend to be expressed more effectively than distal genes. As a result distal genes may be poorly expressed and have very little effect on the susceptibility of the host bacterium to relevant antibiotics.^[28, 59] This explains the variability of antibiotic resistance profile observed among the test pathogens in our study.

Table 7: Antibiotic resistance profile of integron harbouring uropathogens.

Sr. No	Isolate no.	Identified as	ESBL genes	Antibiotic resistance profile		
				Sensitive	Intermediate	Resistance
INTEGRON 1						
1	15	<i>C.diversus</i>	CTX-M	GM, CH, BA,	AS, AK	CF, PC,RC, CI, TE, ZN, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
2	28	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, AmpC, CTX-M	AS, CH, CI, GM, AK	CF,	BA, CF, PC, RC, ZN, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, NA, NX, AG, CU, PB
3	30	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	GM, AK, GF		AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, TE, ZN, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
4	58	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	AS, BA, CH	AK	CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
5	59	<i>C.amalonatus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	PB, BA, CH, RC, ZN, AK, GF		AS, CF, PC, CI, TE, GM, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG
6	68	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M		OX, TE	AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
7	73b	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM	ZN, GM, CH, AS,	RC, AK	BA, CF, PC, CI, TE, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
8	93	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	CH, AK, GF		AS, BA, CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
9	96	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	TE, AK		AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, ZN, GM, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
10	100	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M	AS, BA, CH, RC, TE	CI, CF	CF, PC, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
11	102	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, AmpC, CTX-M	CH, AK	AS	BA, CF, PC, CI, TE, GM, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CP, FG,
12	115	<i>E.coli</i>	CTX-M	CH, GM	AS, CF, AK	BA, PC,RC, CI, TE, ZN, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
13	116	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, AmpC, CTX-M	AS, BA, CH		CF, PC,RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB

14	120	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, AmpC, CTX-M	AS, CH, GM, AK, GF	ZN	BA, CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
15	123	<i>C.diversus</i>	CTX-M	AG, FG	TT, CF	AS, BA, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, CU, CP, PB
16	124	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M		PB, CL, TE	AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
17	130	<i>P.vulgaris</i>	TEM, CTX-M	OX, BA, PC, CI, TE, GM, AK, GF	AS	CF, CH, RC, ZN, TT, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
18	134	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM	AK	OX, AS, GM, GF, TE	BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, ZN, TT, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
19	147	<i>E.coli</i>	CTX-M	AK, GF		AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
20	156	<i>P.vulgaris</i>	TEM, CTX-M	NX, AS, GM, AK	TT, RP, PC, RC, GF	BA, CF, CH, CI, TE, ZN, OX, ZX, CB, NA, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
21	160	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	ZX, AS, BA, CH, ZN, GM, AK, GF	CU, FG	CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, TT, OX, RP, CB, NA, NX, AG, CP, PB
22	166	<i>P.vulgaris</i>	TEM, CTX-M	OX, BA, CH, TE, AK, GF	ZN, GM, PB	AS, CF, PC, RC, CI, TT, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG
23	175	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	OX, CH, CP, TE, AK, GF	PB, ZN	AS, BA, CF, PC, RC, CI, GM, TT, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, FG
24	196	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	TE, AK, AG	TT, OX, NA, RC, GF	AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, CI, ZN, GM, RP, ZX, CB, NX, CU, CP, FG, PB
25	202	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM	RP, ZX, CB, CP, CH, AK	OX, CF, GM, GF	AS, BA, PC, RC, CI, TE, ZN, TT, NA, NX, AG, CU, FG, PB
26	204	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M			AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
27	208	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	CTX-M			AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
28	214	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M			AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
29	216	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M		PB	AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG
30	227	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	GM, AK, GF	PB	AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG
31	233	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M	ZX, CU, PC	CP, CH, AK, GF	AS, BA, CF, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, TT, OX, RP, CB, NA, NX, AG, FG, PB
32	234	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	CH, GF	GM	AS, BA, CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, ZN, AK, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
33	246	<i>E.coli</i>	CTX-M	CH, GF	AK	AS, BA, CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
34	254	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	CH, AK	ZX	AS, BA, CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, GF, TT, OX, RP, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB

35	265	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M		CH, RC, GF	AS, BA, CF, PC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
36	271	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM	OX, TE	ZN, GF	AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, GM, AK, TT, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
37	281	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM			AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
38	290	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	CTX-M	BA, CH	AK, GF	AS, CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
39	306	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M	CH	AK	AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
40	447	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M			TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB, AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF
41	453	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM	AK	PC, RC	AS, BA, CF, CH, CI, TE, ZN, GM, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
42	497	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M		OX, TE	AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
43	500	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	ZN, AK, GF	NX, CU, CP, PB, AS, CF, RC, GM	BA, PC, CH, CI, TE, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, AG, FG
44	536	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M	TT, NA, AG, FG	OX, CU, CP	RP, ZX, CB, NX, PB, AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF
45	593	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM			AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
46	644	<i>C.diversus</i>	TEM, CTX-M	AS, CH, ZN, AK, GF		BA, CF, CH, RC, CI, TE, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
47	687	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM	CH, AK, GF		AS, BA, CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
48	741	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M			AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
49	742	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	CTX-M			AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
50	743	<i>P.aeruginosa</i>	TEM, CTX-M			AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
51	744	<i>K pneumonia</i>	TEM, CTX-M			AS, BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
INTEGRON 2						
52	60	<i>E.aerogenes</i>	TEM	AS, CH	RC	BA, CF, PC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
53	79	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	AS, AK, GM		BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, TE, ZN, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
54	83	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	AS, AK, GM		BA, CF, PC, CH,RC, CI, TE, ZN,

						GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
55	87	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	AS, CH, GM	AK	BA, CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
56	148	<i>E.coli</i>	CTX-M	OX, AS, GM, AK, GF	ZN, TE, CI, RC, CF	BA, PC, CH, TT, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
57	190	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	AS, AK, GF		BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
58	220	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	AS, CH, AK, GF	ZN,	BA, CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, GM, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
59	238	<i>E.coli</i>	CTX-M	GF		AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
60	245	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM, CTX-M	CH, AK, GF	PC	AS, BA, CF, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
61	249	<i>E.coli</i>	TEM	CH, AK		AS, BA, CF, PC, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB
62	730	<i>K.pneumoniae</i>	TEM, CTX-M			AS, BA, CF, PC, CH, RC, CI, TE, ZN, GM, AK, GF, TT, OX, RP, ZX, CB, NA, NX, AG, CU, CP, FG, PB

Integron carriage of resistance gene cassettes by the host bacterium is found to be dependent on the environment that the host organism may be proliferated and, loss of integron-borne resistance genes is observed in the absence of antibiotic selective pressure.^[63]

In the current study, 30.53% and 6.58% ESBL producers carried class 1 and 2 integrons respectively. Another study carried out in a tertiary care hospital in Tehran reported 44% of the ESBL positive isolates to carry class 1 integrons. Also, 6% isolates were found to harbour class 2 integrons. They also found a significant association between integron carriage and higher rates of resistance to β -lactams and other group of antibiotics.^[64] Similar study carried out at Institute of medical sciences, Varanasi, reported presence of class 1 and 2 integrons among 82% and 9% ESBL producers respectively.^[65] A two decade long surveillance study carried out by Yu et al. (2003) reported 54.6% ESBL producing uropathogens to carry class 1 integron in Korean hospitals. They further indicated that the gene cassettes of these uropathogens were continuously changed based on antibiotic selective pressure; and their sizes were increased by the introduction of new cassette genes during the two decades of study. The location of integrons in plasmids may have contributed to the horizontal dissemination of antibiotic resistance gene cassettes. Furthermore, antibiotic resistance genes and gene cassettes associated with metabolites were both introduced into class 1 integrons.^[66]

Machado et al. (2005), indicated in their study, that the selection and spread of genetic elements encoding ESBL has no major role for integron dispersal, except

when bla_{ESBL} genes are within an integron platform, such as $\text{bla}_{\text{CTX-M-9}}$.^[67] In addition, the contribution of integrons to ESBL dissemination seems to be of small significance, as the encoded resistances correspond to old antibiotics without significant intensity of selective pressure in the current clinical setting. They however, proposed that this situation might eventually change, following possible events of selection of specific broad-spectrum plasmids able to capture integrons,^[68,69] or by integron capture of determinants encoding resistances to antibiotics frequently used in the hospital environment.^[70] Surveillance of the integron content of nosocomial *E. coli* populations may be critical to predict and prevent the spread of particular antibiotic resistance determinants.

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